

Surveys of other rotation crops in rice soils under upland conditions showed the infestation of ragi, wheat, and sorghum in that order. Some grasses in and around rice fields (*Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus* sp., *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Eragrostis pilosa*, *Eleusine aegyptica*, and *Cynodon dactylon*) were found to be suitable

hosts for this nematode. In rice followed by the fodder grass crop *Pennisetum pedicellatum*, nematode infestation resulted in 12 to 17% yield loss. A preliminary survey of areas in Kerala, Gujarat, Orissa, West Bengal, and Assam confirmed the prevalence of *P. indicus* in association with rice culture. ❧

Some granular insecticides tested against rice brown spot disease

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To explore their potential for controlling brown spot disease of rice, monocrotophos 5 G, MIPC 4 G, quinalphos 5 G, and AC 92100 5 G, mixed with 20 ml potato-dextrose-agar, were bioassayed against the disease pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan in vitro.

Colony diameter (mm) of mycelial growth of *H. oryzae* 7 days after inoculation ^a(mean of three replicates).

Treatment	Colony diameter (mm) at insecticide doses of				
	1000 ppm	500 ppm	250 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm
Monocrotophos 5 G	—	—	—	—	—
MIPC 4 G	—	—	—	—	—
Quinalphos 5 G	—	—	—	18.3	20.0
A.C. 92, 100	—	15.0	15.6	24.0	30.0
Check	65.0	65.0	65.0	65.0	65.0

^a 8 mm.

The growth of *H. oryzae* was inhibited by all the granular formulations (see table) even at the lowest test dose. It was completely inhibited by monocrotophos and MIPC at the dose of 50 ppm, by quinalphos at 250 ppm, but by AC 92100 5 G only at 1,000 ppm. Granular formulations of the above insecticides may be useful in the control of rice brown spot disease. However, more detailed investigations are needed to prove their potential against *H. oryzae* in the field. ❧

the type of information sought are being modified with experience. The process of station-establishment needs improvement, and states and farmers need to become better prepared to undertake control measures in large areas on short notice.

DPPOS also organizes roving surveys during kharif in Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Assam, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, and West Bengal, chiefly to monitor populations of the tungro vector *Nephotettix virescens*. DPPQS processes the data and issues weekly bulletins. When *N. virescens* counts reach two or three insects per rice hill, state governments are advised to begin control measures. Control alerts are also provided for other pests and diseases. It is planned to extend these roving surveys together areas and other rice seasons.

Following an epidemic in Kerala, DPPQS and the State have also organized a special surveillance program for the brown planthopper. In many cases it now is possible to provide timely warning of upcoming pest problems, although not always possible to institute timely control measures. ❧

Proposed integrated studies of pest control problems

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A study is planned to evolve an integrated picture of the interactions among the pests, pesticides, and nontarget organisms involved in rice culture.

The first part of the study will investigate the action of different organochlorine, organophosphorous, and carbamate pesticides on such nontarget organisms as goats, sheep, rats, frogs, fish, and invertebrates (e.g. mollusks and earthworms). The second part will emphasize the mode of action of the pesticides in important rice pests (e.g. *Tryporyza* sp. and *Chilo* sp.) and the pests' relative sensitivity to different pesticides. Changes in soil chemistry also will be studied.

Several biochemical parameters of target and nontarget organisms, such as

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice surveillance in India

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India is beginning to associate surveillances of rice pests with control measures and research. Among several surveillance programs is a pilot program of the Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine, and Storage (DPPQS) to monitor rice, potatoes, sugarcane, and wheat from Central Surveillance Stations in 12 districts in 9 states. Each

station has a surveillance officer and six field reporters. Each field reporter collects data weekly from 20 fixed fields of the selected block in which he works with sampling equipment, meteorological equipment, and light traps. He also makes a weekly roving survey of a portion of the block. State governments use the surveillance information, along with economic threshold values supplied by the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, to determine need for pest control measures and type of control needed. Sampling methods and